

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: OJEBODE****FIRST NAME: AYODELE****PROGRAM CODE: DIPH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 3%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 11)

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. In conducting dissertation research, students prepare documents to discuss the study and to engage the supervisory committee, including the supervisor. During this stage, choose the single best answer.
 - Students must prepare six documents: a dissertation concept paper, a dissertation prospectus, a dissertation, a dissertation manuscript, abstract, and appendices.
 - A dissertation prospectus and dissertation are usually required, but a dissertation concept paper, if prepared, improves the quality of paper research.¹**

¹ James P. Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, 2nd Edition (Florida State University, Tallahassee, FL, 2017), 2.

- A dissertation manuscript is the only crucial document.
 - Students are open to using any rule of style if all sources are correctly and adequately cited.
2. The dissertation, referred to as the final presentation of the design, execution, and interpretation of the research, has several components. Some components are not mandatorily requested to be part of the document. Choose the best answer.
- Biography and dedication.
 - Dedication, title page, and appendices.
 - Dedication and Acknowledgement.**²
 - Dedication, acknowledgement, and biography.
3. Bias exists in both qualitative and quantitative researches, but takes different positions. Which of the following best describes the positions?
- Researchers are skilled and have the expertise to conduct research; therefore, researchers are not prone to bias.
 - Bias is allowed and commonly acceptable, provided the dissertation provides valid reports and conclusions.
 - Quantitative research promotes objectivity, but qualitative research, on the other hand, contends that bias is inherent.**³

² Sampson, 4.

³ Sampson, 8.

- The ulterior motive is acceptable in designing the research questions as it demonstrates the researchers' passion for the study.
4. Plagiarism is when the writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information. When is it proper to cite or give credit to the author?
- When using any quote, paraphrase, statistic/data, or visuals (such as a graph) that is borrowed from another source.⁴**
- Plagiarism is not a crime provided the material is adequately paraphrased.
- Only when using a direct quote and paraphrasing.
- Internet is a free source and materials copied from this source do not require citations.
5. Citation is the best way to avoid plagiarism and it is required to cite, however citation is not required in certain circumstances. Which of the following best describe a time when citation is not required? Choose the best answer.
- When the information is a common knowledge that can be found in numerous areas, e.g., smoking cause lung cancer.⁵**
- When an information is taken from an unpublished dissertation.
- When the information has no date or author.

⁴ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, Fourth Edition (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 34.

⁵ Cleenewerck and Gulma, 37.

- Citation is not required after a carefully paraphrase statement since the statement are now the writer's word.
6. Colons are punctuation marks commonly used in academic papers to introduce a subclause that follows logically from the text before it, is not a new concept, and depends logically on the preceding main clause. Which of the listed sentences is wrong? Choose the best answer.
- A new drink was introduced to Britain: tea.
- I used to be slim: I will try to lose weight.⁶**
- I would like to be slim: I will try to lose weight.
- We were in trouble this time: the lid had come right off.
7. While paraphrasing, words used must be entirely different from how the original author used those words. A good paraphrase should reflect all the following features except
- It must be your words. The language you use cannot resemble the words of the author.
- The writing style must be different from the style the author used.
- The paraphrased information must be an accurate representation of the author's original statement.
- Change a couple of words, rearrange the sentence structure, and cite the work.⁷**

⁶ Cleenewerck and Gulma, 18.

⁷ Cleenewerck and Gulma, 36.

8. In the Turabian rule of the style, citation helps readers check the work's reliability and further their work. All the listed below are reasons for citation, except:
- To give credit and recognition to the original author.
 - To reassure readers about the accuracy of facts.
 - To establish the first link in that chain of trust by citing sources fully, accurately, and appropriately.
 - To show readers the extent of skill and level of erudite in performing academic research.⁸**
9. The reliability of sources is critical since it is easier to judge the reliability of a reference once it is read to avoid being caught up in a personal ideology or an organization's belief. Which of the ways listed below is not an appropriate way to judge the reliability of a source?
- Examine if a reputable press publishes the source.
 - Review the book or article if peer-reviewed.
 - Determine if the source is current for the field of study.
 - A commercial book that makes extraordinary claims with a Ph.D. author is more reliable than any other source.⁹**

⁸ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, ed. Wayne C. Booth et al., 9th edition, Chicago Guides to Writing, Editing, and Publishing (Chicago London: The University of Chicago Press, 2018), 139-140.

⁹ Turabian, 42.

10. An abstract is one of the components of dissertation research and usually appears at the beginning of the opening page. What are some of the features of a good abstract?

- Abstract occurs within the literature review and summarizes the research.
- The abstract begins with the statement of the problem. It describes the research questions, methodology, and hypotheses, briefly presents the findings, and points to one or two implications as reported in the study.¹⁰**
- An abstract is optional in an academic research paper.
- An abstract is required only if the dissertation manuscript is to be submitted for publication in a peer-reviewed journal.

¹⁰ Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, 33.

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.